

ARMED BANDITRY IN NIGERIA: MAKING MULTIFACETED GOVERNANCE THE EPICENTER OF COUNTER-BANDITRY.

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Abstract: Armed banditry has become a pressing contemporary challenge to Nigeria's national security. Scholars and commentators frequently cite a convergence of factors including entrenched poverty, persistent herder-farmer conflicts, warlordism, ungoverned spaces, cross-border criminal networks, and the proliferation of Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW) as critical factors shaping the country's deteriorating security environment. The rise of armed banditry has triggered everyday killings, kidnappings for ransom, property destruction, and cattle rustling. The concentration of these armed groups in Nigeria's northwestern region, along with the potential for their activities to spread into other geopolitical zones in the country, presents a deeply unsettling scenario for both national and international actors. Such expansion and weaponization of the criminal economy are nerve-racking for the Nigerian state and the international community. In response, the Nigerian government has largely relied on a militarized security strategy to combat banditry. However, while scholarly discourse has increasingly focused on the origins, drivers, and manifestations of this threat, limited attention has been given to the critique of the military-oriented counter-banditry in the region. This study, driven by the need to fill this critical research gap, adopts a qualitative approach grounded primarily in secondary data. This study seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by critically assessing the limitations of Nigeria's predominantly militaristic counter-banditry tactics while suggesting a multifaceted governance as the epicenter of counter-banditry in the country.

Keywords: Armed Banditry, Militarization, Governance, Routine Activity Theory (RAT), Counter-Banditry, Nigeria

Introduction

Banditry has emerged as one of the most alarming forms of criminal activity currently affecting West Africa. Its widespread occurrence and increasing intensity have significantly contributed to regional insecurity and pose a serious threat to the prospects of regional integration across the region (Abdullahi, 2019). Nearly every day, new reports highlight the escalation of bandit attacks targeting farmlands, marketplaces, mining areas, rural settlements, and villages, particularly in countries such as Nigeria, Niger, Burkina Faso, and Mali (Okoli & Ngom, 2021). These developments further undermine regional stability in an already volatile context marked by herder-farmer clashes, ethno-religious violence, and various other forms of armed conflict (UNOWAS Study, 2018).

Armed banditry involves various violent acts such as attacking people on highways, raiding villages, stealing livestock, and engaging in activities like extortion, kidnaping, robbery, and murder. These violent activities in Nigeria have posed a significant threat to national security, peace, and sustainable development. Since around 2011, various states have grappled with the growing menace, which notably escalated between 2011 and 2017. The continued operations of armed bandits have resulted in substantial loss of lives and destruction of property in the affected regions up to the present day (Udosen & Uko, 2021). In Nigeria, banditry occurs mainly in the northwest and north-central regions. It has taken the form of violent attacks on villages, mass kidnappings, and cattle rustling, and it frequently results in displacement, casualties, and local economic disruption (Abdullahi & Mukhtar, 2022). In contrast to insurgency, these bandit groups are often driven by economic rather than ideological goals, taking advantage of porous borders, weak law enforcement, and socio-political vulnerabilities to operate with impunity.

Nigeria ranks among the nation's most severely impacted by banditry. According to a crime report by Ukoji et al. (2019), banditry was responsible for 930 out of 3,425 deaths attributed to various criminal acts across the country. These fatalities spanned 15 states, with Zamfara (714) and Kaduna (100), both located in the northwestern region, accounting for the majority. The remaining deaths were linked to crimes such as kidnaping, cultism, armed robbery, piracy, cattle rustling, ritual killings, and extrajudicial executions, which were reported across all 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Alarming, the frequency of such attacks has continued to escalate across every nook and cranny of the country, indicating a worsening trend. Several underlying causes have been identified as contributors to the growing incidence of banditry in Nigeria. Key among these are climate change, which triggers migration, displacement, and conflict over resources (Ojo et al., 2022); systemic failures in governance exacerbated by corruption; disputes over illegal mining activities, particularly gold; political tensions following electoral losses; erosion of authority at both local and state levels; widespread availability of illicit arms; and the infiltration of insurgent elements such as Boko-Haram. Additionally, Nigeria's poorly governed rural areas, characterized by vast forests and unmonitored borders, have become safe havens for non-state armed groups engaged in cross-border and organized criminal activities (Okoli & Ugwu, 2019; Okoli & Ngom, 2021).

The consequences of banditry go beyond immediate violence. By undermining governmental legitimacy in affected areas, it erodes governance and has resulted in a militarized reaction that raises questions about human rights and the effectiveness of long-term peacebuilding (Odalonu & Egbogu, 2023). As put forward by Abdullahi (2022), the growing threat of armed banditry in Nigeria, particularly in the North-West region, has prompted an increasingly militarized response from the Nigerian state. As banditry evolved into organized violent campaigns involving kidnaping, cattle rustling, and territorial control, the federal government adopted coercive measures, including large-scale military deployments and aerial bombardments in forested bandit enclaves. The adoption of military intervention strategies reflects an acknowledgment that conventional policing is insufficient despite heavily armed non-state actors operating across remote and ungoverned spaces. Military operations such as Operation Hadarin Daji and Operation Thunder Strike have been launched to regain control of contested territories, dismantle bandit strongholds, and enhance the protection of vulnerable civilians (Madubuegwu & Abah, 2023). While these missions have recorded certain operational successes, they have fallen short in addressing the structural drivers of banditry or establishing lasting peace. Observers have raised concerns that over-reliance on kinetic strategies has produced counterproductive outcomes, including civilian casualties,

violations of human rights, and increasing alienation of local populations from state authorities (Thompson et al., 2024).

The lack of accompanying development programs or post-conflict rehabilitation measures often leaves the affected communities more vulnerable and susceptible to renewed cycles of violence. The situation is further complicated by the widespread availability of illicit firearms and the increasing overlap between state security functions and the activities of informal armed groups. Community vigilante organizations and local self-defense militias occasionally operating with the approval or support of governmental actors have also stepped into the security void. However, their involvement has at times escalated inter-communal conflicts and weakened centralized security governance (Aina, 2024). In essence, although the militarized response reflects the state's commitment to restoring order, it must be integrated with comprehensive governance reforms, inclusive community engagement, and strategic socio-economic development initiatives. Without these complementary efforts, reliance on the militarization approach risks entrenching insecurity rather than resolving it (Ojo, Oyewole, & Aina, 2023). In addition, the way that banditry intersects with other security issues like farmer-herder disputes and inter-communal violence compounds the complexity of Nigeria's security environment (Joab-Peterside, 2020). This research argues that a multifaceted approach of credible governance that includes enforcement reforms, socio-economic development, intelligence collection, and community-based conflict resolution will be more instrumental in addressing these intertwined challenges than the usual militarized security strategy of the Nigerian state.

Conceptual Discourse: Armed Banditry in Nigeria

Nigeria, situated in West Africa, is the continent's most populous nation, with an estimated population exceeding 200 million individuals. Renowned for its ethnic diversity, Nigeria is home to the broadest array of ethnic groups and linguistic communities on the African continent (Campbell, 2011). The country is administratively structured into 36 states along with the Federal Capital Territory, which are further segmented into 774 Local Government Areas (LGAs) (Abdul-Raheem, 2020). A significant portion of the Nigerian populace, approximately 70%, resides in rural communities where subsistence farming remains the primary livelihood (Oluwole et al., 2021). Economic hardship is pervasive, with more than half the population, about 136 million people either living in extreme poverty, defined as surviving on less than \$2.15 per day, or being at substantial risk of falling into poverty (World Bank, 2022). Banditry in Nigeria has deep historical roots embedded in the country's socio-political and economic dynamics. Traditionally, the term described the actions of armed groups operating in both rural and semi-urban regions, who engaged in cattle rustling, ambushes on travelers, and village raids. In northern Nigeria, such activities date back to the pre-colonial era, when inter-communal disputes, competition for pastoral resources, and cross-border raids were prevalent among nomadic and agrarian communities (Ojewale, 2023). The colonial period intensified these dynamics through the British administration's disruption of indigenous governance systems and failure to invest in rural infrastructure. This neglect marginalized certain communities and created structural vulnerabilities that allowed criminal practices like banditry to take hold (Okoli & Abubakar, 2021). Following independence, these trends persisted as many rural areas remained underdeveloped, poorly governed, and inadequately secured, thereby sustaining conditions conducive to banditry.

Armed banditry encompasses a range of violent criminal acts, including kidnaping, theft, armed assault, and destruction of property (Osasona, 2023). When viewed through the lens of organized crime, banditry in Nigeria is fundamentally driven by the pursuit of illicit economic gain. These criminal networks often engage in violent acts such as property damage, civilian casualties, and the forcible acquisition of valuables (Osasona, 2023). In

this framework, armed bandits function as structured criminal groups that target communities, seizing money, livestock, and sometimes committing sexual violence (Ojo et al., 2023). Unlike ideologically motivated terrorist groups such as al-Qaeda, Boko Haram, ISIS, or Al-Shabaab, bandit groups in Nigeria operate without a formal ideological agenda. As noted by Ojewale (2023), these groups demonstrate elements of organizational structure akin to global militias, including hierarchical command and control mechanisms. Their operations are primarily concentrated in the rural areas of the country, where they are heavily armed with sophisticated weapons like AK-47 rifles. The prevalence of banditry in these regions is largely attributed to limited governmental oversight and the absence of effective policing and state authority. In these ungoverned spaces, armed bandits exploit lawlessness to assert control. Their activities revolve around economic acquisition through acts of coercion, including looting, robbery, intimidation, and physical violence (Obi & Iwuoha, 2023). This also involves the expropriation of means of livelihood, particularly livestock, which is subsequently sold for profit. Research literature identifies the primary ethnic groups engaged in armed banditry in Nigeria as Fulani, Hausa, Kanuri, and other ethnic communities. These groups often use Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW) to execute their criminal operations (Obi & Iwuoha, 2023; Ojo, 2020).

In the early 21st century, particularly in Nigeria's northwest, banditry took on a new dimension. It emerged as a convergence of unresolved farmer-herder conflicts, the widespread availability of illicit firearms, and a growing black market for cattle and ransom payments (Idowu & Arua, 2023). This period witnessed a shift from opportunistic theft to more organized, militarized bandit groups operating across state borders. These groups engage in mass abductions, extortion, and the control of territory, often with impunity due to the state's weak enforcement capacity (Bello, Agunyai, & Amusan, 2022). By the 2010s, the situation had deteriorated significantly. Bandit networks gained access to advanced weaponry and developed sophisticated operational tactics. These groups now dominate forest regions and major rural routes, effectively undermining the state's control and contributing to a crisis on par with terrorism in scale and severity. They are also involved in various criminal enterprises such as cattle theft, illicit mining, and arms trafficking. In some localities, bandits have established quasi-governments, collecting taxes and dispensing "justice" in the absence of state control (Okoli & Abubakar, 2021; Bello et al., 2022). The evolution of banditry in Nigeria thus reflects broader trends in the country's governance failures, economic inequalities, and security lapses. Understanding its historical roots is critical for designing effective countermeasures that address both the symptoms and underlying causes of the Menace

Furthermore, banditry has inflicted severe consequences on the Nigerian society. Widespread kidnappings, including the abduction of hundreds of schoolchildren, have led to the closure of schools and markets, with estimates indicating that over one million children have been forced out of school as a result (Jacob & Ndubuisi, 2021). In several rural communities, residents have been compelled to abandon their homes and farms due to violent attacks involving the destruction of grain storage facilities and theft of livestock (Abang, 2021). Moreover, banditry has disrupted transportation and trade across regional borders, including the closure of roads critical to the movement of goods and food supplies (Ladan & Badaru, 2021). These disruptions have triggered a large-scale humanitarian crisis, displacing hundreds of thousands within the country and forcing others to seek refuge in neighboring nations (Jones et al., 2021). The cumulative effect has been the deterioration of security nationwide. Compounding this issue, Nigeria has also witnessed a surge in violent extremism, particularly in the northeastern region where Islamist militant activity has intensified, alongside the rising incidence of farmer-herder clashes in the central part of the country (Adamu & Ekere, 2020; Darma, 2021). Boko Haram, which originated in the 1990s,

transitioned into a full-fledged terrorist organization by the early 2000s and fragmented into multiple jihadist factions by 2016 (Barnett et al., 2022). These groups have conducted deadly attacks against security forces and critical infrastructure, leading to tens of thousands of deaths and the displacement of millions (Jones et al., 2021). Simultaneously, conflicts between herders and farmers have escalated, driven by fierce competition over natural resources such as pasture and water. These clashes have intensified ethnic divisions and have resulted in considerable fatalities (Onah et al., 2021). Environmental changes, especially those associated with climate change, have further intensified the scarcity of vital resources (Abubakar et al., 2020; Erundu & Nwakanma, 2018). In northern Nigeria, over half the land is turning into desert (Garba, 2021), while the national cattle population has surged from nine million in the 1970s to approximately twenty-five million by 2016 (Erundu & Nwakanma, 2018). Collectively, these multifaceted security, social, and environmental crises have raised concerns among scholars and policymakers about Nigeria being described as a failed state. Some argue that the country exhibits characteristics of state failure, a scenario long predicted by analysts (Nwaechefu et al., 2021).

Theoretical Framework: Routine Activity Theory

A range of theoretical frameworks can be employed to interpret the growing incidence of banditry in Nigeria. Among the most relevant are the frustration-aggression theory, relational vengeance theory, situational action theory, relative deprivation theory, strain theory, and the queer ladder of mobility theory. Each offers distinct insights into the psychological, social, and structural drivers underpinning violent criminal behavior. On the contrary, this research has preferably considered Routine Activity Theory (RAT) suitable to the position of its submissions to the debate of banditry in Nigeria within the existing literature. The surge in banditry, particularly in Nigeria's northwestern region, has drawn increasing attention from scholars and policymakers, prompting them to explore its underlying causes through established criminological theories. One such theoretical approach is the Routine Activity Theory (RAT), introduced by Cohen and Felson in 1979. This framework interprets crime as a product of the simultaneous presence of three critical components: a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the absence of an effective guardian. Applying this model to the Nigerian context helps illuminate why banditry continues to thrive, especially in under-governed rural and semi-urban communities. Routine Activity Theory suggests that criminal acts are most likely to occur when a willing offender encounters an appealing target in a setting lacking preventive measures or capable deterrents (Cohen & Felson, 1979). Rather than focusing on the inherent traits of offenders, RAT examines the environmental and enabling factors, such as daily routines and weak security frameworks that provide fertile ground for criminal activity.

In Nigeria, banditry typically includes violent crimes such as armed robberies, kidnappings, cattle rustling, and raids on rural settlements. These behaviors align with the core elements of RAT in the following ways: (1) **Motivated Offenders:** many individuals involved in banditry are drawn from economically and socially marginalized populations, including unemployed and uneducated youth, former herders, and criminal syndicates. They are often driven by poverty, retaliation, or the lure of economic advantages (Ejiofor, 2022). (2) **Suitable Targets:** residents of rural areas, travelers, herders, and students frequently become the targets of attacks due to their exposure and lack of protection. The ease of targeting these vulnerable groups makes them particularly attractive to offenders (Odalonu, 2023). (3) **Lack of Capable Guardians:** the vast ungoverned spaces and porous borders in Nigeria create environments where state security is largely absent. The limited presence of law enforcement, combined with the delayed response times from the military, allows bandits to act without significant deterrence (Ojo, 2020). In addition, environmental dynamics and routine exposure are another enabling factor for banditry in the country. This involves the everyday practices of rural populations, such as

farming, fetching water, or traveling between villages—are highly predictable and often carried out in isolated locations. These conditions make them especially vulnerable to attacks. Additionally, the routine transport of goods and people along unsecured routes presents repeated opportunities for criminals to stage ambushes and kidnappings, illustrating how daily patterns create ongoing risk (Onwuzuruigbo, 2020). Interpreting banditry through the RAT framework highlights the value of situational crime prevention. Strategies such as bolstering community-based policing, deploying surveillance technologies (e.g., drones and patrol systems), and modifying routine activities such as organizing escorted travel or implementing curfews in vulnerable zones could significantly reduce crime opportunities. Moreover, addressing the governance void in rural areas by re-establishing law enforcement and rebuilding public confidence is essential. RAT is suitably considered for this research because it provides a compelling explanatory framework for understanding the spatial and temporal patterns of banditry in Nigeria. By focusing on the conditions that created an enabling environment for banditry, namely, motivated offenders, vulnerable targets, and absent guardians, RAT offers actionable insights for both academic research and practical policymaking aimed at curbing insecurity.

Causes of Armed Banditry in Nigeria

Many scholars, including Gaye (2018), Olaniyan & Yahaya (2016), Suleiman (2017), and Mustapha (2019), have identified multiple underlying causes for the rise and persistence of banditry in Nigeria. Their analyses point to the fragility of the Nigerian state and the ineffectiveness of its institutional structures, especially within the security sector, as critical enablers of the crisis. Contributing factors include the existence of vast ungoverned territories, poorly secured borders with neighboring countries, and the widespread availability of illicit firearms. Additional issues such as deficient leadership, systemic corruption, rampant unemployment, and widespread poverty further intensify the insecurity. Moreover, although Nigeria was founded on a federalist structure, its security system remains highly centralized. Since the military's incursion into politics, control over all national security agencies has been concentrated in the hands of the President, limiting subnational autonomy in addressing local security challenges. The following factors have been identified as the drivers of armed banditry in the country:

A. Poverty and Unemployment: one of the primary drivers of armed banditry in Nigeria is widespread poverty and unemployment, particularly among youths. Many young people in rural areas are idle and easily recruited into banditry networks, which offer financial incentives through ransom payments and stolen goods. The socioeconomic deprivation in these regions often leaves banditry as one of the few viable sources of livelihood (Idowu & Arua, 2023; Valentine, 2023). According to Idowu and Arua (2023), the high incidence of armed banditry in northwest Nigeria correlates strongly with extreme poverty levels and economic marginalization. Many rural youths, disillusioned by the state's failure to provide jobs or meaningful livelihood programs, are recruited into bandit groups that offer immediate financial rewards. These groups promise payments from ransoms, stolen livestock, or protection rackets, which are often more lucrative than traditional agricultural labor or informal sector work. Valentine (2023) highlights that poverty has a direct impact on both the supply and demand sides of criminality: those who suffer economic deprivation are more likely to join banditry, while impoverished communities lack the resources to defend themselves or collaborate effectively with law enforcement. Moreover, the socioeconomic effects of banditry, such as displacement, destruction of farmlands, and closure of schools, further deepen poverty, creating a vicious cycle of insecurity and economic decline.

B. Weak Governance and Corruption: Weak state institutions, poor governance, and endemic corruption have significantly eroded public trust in the government's ability to maintain security and justice. These factors

undermine the effectiveness of state institutions, erode public trust in the government, and create the conditions under which criminality can flourish. When state authority is absent or dysfunctional, non-state actors, including bandit groups, often step in to fill the power vacuum, frequently imposing their own rules and systems of control over rural communities. The absence of effective law enforcement and judicial mechanisms creates a vacuum often filled by bandits, who exploit this power gap to establish control over rural territories (Bello, Agunyai, & Amusan, 2022). In some instances, local officials are complicit or incapable of resisting criminal activities, further entrenching the influence of armed groups (Okoli & Abubakar, 2021). According to Bello, Agunyai, and Amusan (2022), the weakness of law enforcement institutions, compounded by a lack of political will and inter-agency rivalry, has allowed banditry to escalate from localized crime to a full-scale security crisis. The government's failure to provide basic services and protect citizens in affected regions diminishes its legitimacy and opens the door for criminal groups to exert influence and gain support from disaffected populations. Moreover, corruption among political elites and security agencies hampers the effective deployment of counter-banditry strategies. In many cases, military and police personnel are accused of colluding with or accepting bribes from bandits to look the other way or provide protection (Ruwandoruwa & Umar, 2024).

C. Farmer-Herder Conflicts and Environmental Stress: The interplay between farmer-herder conflicts and environmental stress is a critical driver of armed banditry in Nigeria, particularly in the country's northwestern and central regions. As land and water resources become increasingly scarce due to climate change, desertification, and deforestation, the competition between sedentary farmers and nomadic herders intensifies, often erupting into violent confrontations. These recurring clashes create fertile ground for the emergence and entrenchment of armed groups, many of which evolve into organized bandit networks. Ojewale (2023) explains that diminishing environmental resources have severely disrupted traditional grazing and farming patterns, leading herders to encroach upon farmlands in search of pasture. In response, farmers whose crops and livelihoods are threatened retaliate, triggering cycles of violence. Over time, these local disputes escalate, drawing in armed actors who capitalize on the instability to assert territorial control, extract rents, and enforce their authority through violence. Environmental stress, particularly in the arid and semi-arid northern zones, has worsened due to recurrent droughts and erratic rainfall patterns, which reduce agricultural productivity and force both farmers and herders to migrate in search of sustenance (Idowu & Arua, 2023). This migratory pressure intensifies land-use competition and often places previously peaceful communities into direct conflict. Bandit groups have exploited these tensions by recruiting aggrieved or displaced individuals and offering them protection, weapons, or economic opportunities through criminal enterprise. Moreover, the failure of the Nigerian government to implement effective land-use policies or invest in conflict-sensitive environmental management has intensified the problem. Rather than addressing the root causes of the farmer-herder crisis, such as land tenure insecurity, population pressure, and inadequate grazing reserves, state responses have largely been reactive, focusing on military interventions that do not resolve underlying grievances (Enodien & Eze, 2024). In sum, environmental degradation and farmer-herder conflicts are not isolated issues but are deeply interconnected with the broader security challenges in Nigeria. Addressing these issues requires an integrated approach that combines environmental management, land reform, and inclusive conflict-resolution mechanisms.

D. Proliferation of Small Arms and Border Porosity: the proliferation of small arms and light weapons (SALWs), coupled with Nigeria's porous borders, play a significant role in fueling armed banditry across the country. The widespread availability of illicit weapons has escalated the scale and intensity of violence, enabling bandit groups to conduct coordinated attacks, sustain criminal networks, and challenge the authority of state

security forces. This situation is exacerbated by weak border management and insufficient surveillance across Nigeria's vast and often unmonitored frontier zones. According to Akinyetun and Bakare (2022), most weapons used by bandit groups in northern Nigeria are smuggled through the porous borders shared with Niger, Chad, and Cameroon. These borders are inadequately policed, allowing arms traffickers and criminal elements to move freely. Nigeria's participation in the larger Sahel region, which has experienced a surge in armed insurgencies and state collapse, has also contributed to the spillover of illegal arms into the country. Weapons initially intended for regional conflicts often end up in the hands of bandits operating in Nigeria's northwest. The influx of SALWs has emboldened non-state actors by increasing their firepower and enabling more lethal operations, including mass kidnappings, village raids, and ambushes of military convoys. Udosen and Uwak (2021) argue that the sheer volume of unregulated arms circulating in Nigeria not only empowers criminal groups but also undermines the state's monopoly on violence, a fundamental principle of sovereign governance. The lack of effective tracking mechanisms and regulatory enforcement means that once arms enter Nigeria, they are easily traded or redistributed among different criminal factions. Furthermore, weak border governance is often the result of corruption, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient funding for customs and immigration services. Security officials at border posts are sometimes complicit in arms trafficking, either through negligence or active collaboration with smugglers (Ruwandoruwa & Umar, 2024). This has allowed for a thriving black market in arms and ammunition, especially in conflict-prone states such as Zamfara, Katsina, and Sokoto. The security implications are far-reaching. The increased availability of weapons has transformed what were once low-level opportunistic crimes into large-scale organized armed banditry. It has also made conflict resolution more difficult, as armed groups resist demobilization and negotiate from positions of strength (Okoli & Abubakar, 2021). To combat the proliferation of SALWs and its impact on armed banditry, Nigeria must invest in modern border surveillance technologies, strengthen regional cooperation, and enforce stricter controls on arms imports and distribution. Addressing this root cause is essential for reducing the capacity of bandit groups and restoring state authority in affected regions.

E. Ungoverned Spaces and Porous Borders: ungoverned or ill-governed spaces refer to areas where state authority is weak, absent, or contested. In Nigeria, vast forested regions, particularly in the northwest, have become safe havens for bandits. These areas allow criminal groups to operate training camps, establish informal governance structures, and launch attacks without immediate state intervention. For example, Onwuzuruigbo (2020) highlights how ungoverned forest spaces have facilitated cattle rustling and banditry, with criminal groups effectively establishing their own governance systems (Onwuzuruigbo, 2020). Similarly, Ojo (2020) argues that the lack of formal governance in these areas fosters radicalization and arms trafficking, turning them into potential incubators for terrorism and large-scale violence (Ojo, 2020). Furthermore, the Nigerian state's inability to assert control over its full territory is linked to state fragility. Okoye et al. (2025) pointed out that the state's weak presence allows various armed groups to use these areas as operational bases, thereby perpetuating insecurity and banditry (Okoye et al., 2025).

Nigeria's borders with neighboring countries are notoriously porous, allowing the unregulated flow of people, arms, and goods. This facilitates the movement of criminal groups and enables them to evade arrest by simply crossing into neighboring states. Odalonu (2023) underscores how porous borders contribute to the proliferation of arms and facilitate the inflow of foreign bandits into Nigeria (Odalonu, 2023). Obikaeze et al. (2023) link the ECOWAS protocol on free movement with increasing security threats, noting that the unregulated migration has burdened Nigeria's already strained security architecture (Obikaeze et al., 2023). Similarly, Udosen and Uwak

(2021) explain how porous borders facilitate the trafficking of weapons and illicit goods, which directly fuels banditry (Udosen & Uwak, 2021). The interplay between ungoverned spaces and porous borders highlights that these two factors often operate in tandem. Ungoverned spaces within Nigeria serve as domestic hideouts, while porous borders offer international escape routes and channels for arms smuggling. Sackflame and Omitola (2022) describe how bandits use ungoverned territories to contest state sovereignty, undermining national development and security goals (Sackflame & Omitola, 2022).

Implications of Banditry on Nigeria's National Security

Within the framework of the modern state, banditry is widely recognized as a significant threat to national security. This is due to the fact that security generally encompasses not only the fulfillment of basic human needs but also the broader issue of protecting the survival of individuals and the state itself. Banditry entails a range of unlawful and violent activities, often perpetrated with the use of firearms and other deadly weapons, posing serious challenges to national security. National security is defined by a state's capacity to defend its sovereignty, uphold institutional stability, and ensure the protection and welfare of its citizens through the maintenance of safety and sustained development. The menace of banditry undermines national security by inflicting widespread destruction on lives and property, devastating agricultural outputs, and fueling the circulation of illegal arms, which in turn supports further violence and organized criminal activities. According to a report published by The Guardian on April 13, 2019, the intensification of bandit attacks in certain parts of Nigeria has resulted in widespread killings, arson, and a breakdown of law and order. The report further asserted that both national and human development in the most affected regions have been severely disrupted. Bandits are reported to engage in wanton violence, taking the lives of defenseless rural dwellers, demolishing their homes, abducting travelers and herders, and extorting families through ransom demands after rustling livestock for profit.

In recent years, Nigeria's national security has faced significant challenges due to the rapid expansion of armed banditry, particularly in the northwestern and central parts of the country. What once seemed like sporadic rural criminality has escalated into a profound security emergency with widespread national impact. Banditry in the Nigerian context is characterized by violent attacks, large-scale kidnappings, cattle rustling, and village raids, often orchestrated by well-armed criminal groups operating in areas with minimal government presence (ungoverned spaces). This analysis examines the far-reaching consequences of banditry, focusing on its effects on national security infrastructure, economic stability, and societal cohesion. The increasing number of fatalities linked to banditry, alongside the widespread availability of small arms and light weapons in northern Nigeria, has significantly heightened the nation's security crisis. These weapons have played a critical role in escalating organized criminal activities such as cattle rustling, kidnappings, and acts of terrorism, all of which collectively hinder societal progress and development. The pervasive insecurity caused by banditry has become a nationwide concern, affecting all segments of society. Public spaces including educational institutions, residential areas, and marketplaces, religious centers such as mosques and churches and major transportation routes have become frequent targets of bandit attacks (Usman & Singh, 2021). The deteriorating security landscape is especially pronounced in northern Nigeria, where despite the long-standing brutality of Boko Haram, the threat of banditry continues to persist. The situation is particularly alarming in states such as Zamfara, Katsina, Kano, Kaduna, Sokoto, Nassarawa, Benue, and Niger and has extended into the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja (Usman & Singh, 2021). According to Ojewale (2021), banditry now accounts for approximately 40% of the security challenges confronting the nation, as outlined in Nigeria's National Security Strategy. Some implications of banditry on Nigeria's national security can be explained as follows:

A. Territorial Fragmentation and Weakening of State Authority: one of the most immediate consequences of armed banditry in Nigeria is the diminishing presence and effectiveness of state control in certain regions. Bandit groups have taken advantage of ungoverned forest regions and Nigeria's insecure borders to establish fortified enclaves, where they exert considerable influence over local communities (Ojo, 2020; Onwuzuruigbo, 2020). In these territories, state authority is either completely absent or actively contested, eroding the state's monopoly on legitimate violence or undermining its sovereign authority (Okoye et al., 2025).

B. Increased the incidence of Unemployment and Poverty: The rise in banditry has significantly contributed to deepening poverty levels in Nigeria's Northwestern region. This part of the country already ranks among the poorest when assessed through indicators of multidimensional poverty, which include living standards, access to education, and health services. In terms of living conditions, banditry has stripped victims of essential assets such as personal property, commercial enterprises, and livelihood resources crucial for their economic well-being. The economic activities of both subsistence and commercial farmers and herders have been severely disrupted, with many being forced to abandon their farmlands, livestock, and cattle. This disruption has intensified poverty, heightened unemployment, and intensified social exclusion and marginalization across the northern region (Akinyetun, Bakare, & Oke, 2022).

C. Threat to Internal Security and Lives: armed banditry has significantly heightened internal security risks through frequent acts of violence, including abductions for ransom, destruction of property, and lethal attacks. These incidents have triggered large-scale displacement, leading to an internal refugee crisis that has deepened Nigeria's humanitarian challenges (Brigid et al., 2022). Additionally, the growing sense of lawlessness and fear further destabilizes regions already susceptible to insurgency and communal conflict. As of March 2020, it was estimated that over 210,000 individuals had been internally displaced within Nigeria due to escalating insecurity, while an additional 35,000 refugees had fled across the border into Maradi, Niger Republic (Mac-Leva, 2021). The influx of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) into host communities has intensified competition for limited essential resources, including water, arable land, and food supplies (Mac-Leva, 2021). According to Egwu (2016), the rise in banditry has triggered a severe humanitarian crisis marked by mass displacement, forced migration, widespread fatalities, and rampant cattle theft. Additionally, the violence has contributed to significant rural-to-urban migration, as individuals from conflict-affected areas abandon their homes in search of safety in cities, fearing renewed attacks (Akinyetun, Bakare, & Oke, 2022). The conditions within the IDP camps pose further public health challenges. Inadequate access to clean water, overcrowding, and unsanitary environments including open defecation and poorly maintained toilet facilities have heightened the risk of disease outbreaks such as cholera and diarrhea (ACAPS, 2020). The displacement resulting from these attacks has also undermined adherence to public health guidelines, including COVID-19 protocols, exposing vulnerable populations to additional health threats (Bashir, 2021).

D. Economic Disruption and Rural Collapse: the intensification of banditry has severely disrupted agricultural activities and rural economic systems. The forced displacement of farming populations has led to decreased food production, contributing to inflation and heightened food insecurity (Idemudia & Boehnke, 2020). This breakdown of rural livelihoods fuels a cycle of economic vulnerability and insecurity and pressures urban centers with rising numbers of displaced individuals seeking safety and economic relief (Odalonu, 2023). Igbini (2020) observed that banditry has significantly undermined Nigeria's socio-economic and political stability, with the Northwest region being particularly affected. The rise in violent activities has stifled key economic sectors, including agriculture, commerce, and mineral exploration, while also deterring foreign investors. As a result,

livelihoods have been severely disrupted, and widespread fear and insecurity have taken hold among local populations (Mac-Leva, 2021).

E. Impediment to National Development Goals: Chronic insecurity caused by banditry poses a substantial barrier to Nigeria's developmental agenda. The reallocation of public resources toward military and humanitarian interventions hampers progress in infrastructure, education, healthcare, and poverty alleviation. Insecurity discourages foreign investment and stalls the implementation of development programs. According to Sackflame and Omitola (2022), the atmosphere of insecurity threatens Nigeria's progress toward achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in sectors such as education, health, and poverty reduction.

F. Strained Regional and Diplomatic Relations: the cross-border dimension of banditry facilitated by Nigeria's porous borders has complicated its diplomatic ties with neighboring countries. Bandit groups often conduct operations that spill into countries such as Chad and Niger, creating transnational security concerns and necessitating regional security collaboration (Obikaeze et al., 2023). These developments have heightened international perceptions of Nigeria as a source of regional instability, affecting both its geopolitical standing and its appeal to global investors or foreign direct investment.

G. Militarization and Human Rights Concerns: the Nigerian government's counter-banditry strategy has leaned heavily on military interventions, resulting in the increased militarization of affected regions. Although such efforts have yielded tactical gains, they have also raised significant human rights issues and failed to address the socio-economic root causes of banditry. As Ejiofor (2022) contends, over-reliance on military force risks alienating local populations, worsening grievances, and complicating long-term peacebuilding.

Militaristic Counter-Banditry Tactics of the Nigerian State

Over the years, Nigerian security agencies have adopted a range of tactics in their efforts to curb banditry. Initially, the federal government implemented a forceful approach by deploying both police and military personnel to key northern states such as Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Niger, and Sokoto. These operations involved counterattacks against the bandits, the destruction of their camps, and the arrest or elimination of hundreds of operatives. Despite these measures, bandit activities persisted. In 2019, efforts were made to engage in dialogue, resulting in an agreement between the bandit leaders and the governors of Katsina, Sokoto, and Zamfara. The terms of the agreement included disarmament, the liberation of the abducted individuals, and amnesty for the perpetrators. Although these peace-building efforts initially led to a decline in violence between August and November, attacks resumed the following year (Dami, 2021). Both federal and state governments have also been implicated in the payment of ransoms, often to ensure the safety and release of hostages, although officials frequently deny such actions (Johns, 2014; Mustapha, 2019). This practice has inadvertently transformed mass abductions into a lucrative enterprise for criminal and extremist groups. The financial incentive of ransom payments has, in turn, encouraged the continuation of these illicit activities.

According to Ojewale (2023), the mainstream policing model is described as one of the Nigerian state's responses to banditry. The Nigeria Police Force (NPF) is constitutionally responsible for upholding law and order within the country's security framework. Its principal function centers on mainstream policing, which includes intelligence gathering, identification and protection of vulnerable targets, and providing immediate response to various threats. This responsibility also encompasses strategic risk planning, issuing early warnings, and cooperating with local communities. Mainstream policing is particularly effective when undertaken by local officers, as their routine engagement with the community enhances their ability to observe, collect grassroots

intelligence, and build trust-based relationships. Several operational successes illustrate the intelligence-driven nature of mainstream policing. For instance, in October 2021, specialized anti-banditry units of the police, acting on credible intelligence, launched operations in the Gidan Bitu, Malakar, and Kagara forests. This led to the apprehension of a prominent bandit leader and the neutralization of five others during a raid in the Gummi Local Government Area (News Agency of Nigeria, 2021). Similarly, in December of the same year, a suspect involved in arms supply to criminal groups in Katsina and Zamfara was arrested (Oyelude, 2021). Another notable example occurred in September 2021, when police operatives apprehended three women accused of selling fuel to bandits operating near the Jibia forest in Katsina State. This incident followed the arrest of transnational offenders from Maradi, Niger Republic, for similar activities involving the supply of fuel to armed groups hiding in the forests of Katsina (Maishanu, 2021). These cases underscore the significance of intelligence-led policing as a fundamental component of Nigeria's strategy to combat banditry. They reflect a broader, integrated approach aimed at enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of preventive and responsive security measures.

Another adopted method for curbing armed banditry in the country is known as the vigilante model. In light of the growing threat posed by armed banditry and the limited effectiveness of Nigerian security agents, vigilante groups have emerged as a key form of grassroots defense in many communities. These locally organized groups have become instrumental in countering banditry, especially in rural areas where state security forces are either absent or insufficient. While they have helped bridge critical security gaps, their existence also raises complex issues concerning legality, accountability, and the broader implications for the state's monopoly on the use of force. Examples of such community defense groups include the Yan Sakai, active in Zamfara and Katsina States, and the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) in Borno State. These groups were created by residents aiming to protect their communities from ongoing violence by bandits and insurgents. Their operations typically depend on deep-rooted local knowledge, collective responsibility, and access to informal intelligence networks to identify and confront security threats (Ojewale, 2023). In many instances, their responsiveness and effectiveness have surpassed that of conventional police forces, which often struggle with logistical constraints, corruption, and a shortage of personnel (Abraham & Sakariyau, 2023).

The rise of vigilante groups also signifies the collapse of trust in the Nigerian security architecture. Faced with repeated failures by the police and military, many communities opt for localized defense mechanisms. According to Gulbi et al. (2024), some communities place greater trust in vigilantes, viewing them as more committed to protecting local interests and less prone to corruption. However, despite their contributions to community safety, these groups have been accused of extrajudicial killings, human rights abuses, and retaliatory attacks, especially when suspects are caught without due process. Allegations of extrajudicial killings, human rights violations, and violent reprisals are common, particularly when suspected criminals are apprehended without legal safeguards (Ojewale, 2023). Furthermore, there have been cases where vigilante units were infiltrated by criminal actors or evolved into armed militias advancing specific ethnic or sectarian agendas, thereby aggravating local tensions. To address these challenges, some scholars advocate the formal incorporation of vigilante groups into Nigeria's broader security strategy. Ojewale (2023), for instance, proposes a plural policing model, where vigilantes operate in conjunction with state forces under a regulated framework to enhance community policing and reduce human rights violations. However, careful policy design is essential to avoid legitimizing unlawful violence or undermining the state's authority over the legitimate use of force.

The third adopted counter-banditry method of the Nigerian state is identified as the militarization approach, which involves the deployment of military armed forces. The Nigerian government has increasingly relied on joint

security task forces as a strategic response to the escalating threat of armed banditry, especially in the northern regions. The Joint Task Force (JTF) model involves collaboration among the Nigerian Army, Air Force, Police, Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC), and other security agencies. These multi-agency forces are deployed to conduct coordinated military-style operations aimed at neutralizing bandit groups, reclaiming territories, and restoring security in conflict-prone areas. One of the most prominent examples is Operation Whirl Punch, launched in Kaduna State to counter rising banditry, kidnaping, and cattle rustling. This operation combined intelligence gathering, aerial surveillance, and ground offensives to dismantle known bandit camps and dislodge criminal elements from forested hideouts (Anthony, Sunday, & William, 2024). The deployment of the JTF under this operation has led to the arrest and elimination of several high-profile bandits and the rescue of kidnaped victims. However, the operation's success has been constrained by issues such as limited logistics, poor inter-agency coordination, and lack of real-time intelligence.

Similarly, Operation Hadarin Daji, a large-scale joint task force launched in 2019, targets banditry across multiple states including Zamfara, Sokoto, Katsina, and Kebbi. This JTF has conducted sustained air raids and ground offensives, leading to the destruction of bandit enclaves in ungoverned forest areas such as the Rugu Forest. The operation has been particularly lauded for its use of aerial firepower and collaboration with local vigilantes to navigate complex terrains (Ojewale, 2023). Despite its achievements, critics argue that the gains of the operation are often temporary, with bandits adapting quickly and relocating to new areas due to Nigeria's porous borders and lack of follow-up stabilization efforts (Okoli & Abubakar, 2021). The JTF approach is praised for its inter-agency synergy, which brings together the complementary skills and resources of different forces. For example, the military provides combat strength and aerial capabilities, while the police handle arrests and legal procedures. However, the sustainability of these operations is often questioned due to funding limitations, human rights concerns, and allegations of civilian casualties during raids (Bello, Agunyai, & Amusan, 2022). Importantly, the absence of a clear exit strategy for JTF deployments also raises concerns. Once operations wind down, the affected areas often experience a resurgence of criminal activity due to a vacuum in local security governance. Thus, experts have emphasized the need to link JTF operations with long-term solutions such as local policing reform, community-based intelligence, and rural development initiatives (Ojewale, 2023). In conclusion, while the Joint Task Force model has proven to be an effective short-term military response to armed banditry in Nigeria, its long-term success depends on institutional reform, sustained funding, and integration with civilian security and development strategies.

In January 2021, the joint security task force successfully thwarted an attempted bandit attack on Erena town in the Shiroro Local Government Area, Niger State (Oladipo, 2021). Later, in March 2021, the Joint Security Task Force neutralized at least 15 suspected bandits in the Bassa community, also in the Shiroro LGA. During the operation, the authorities seized 15 motorcycles and several high-powered firearms, including AK-47 rifles (This Day, 2021). Operations continued into 2022, with a March campaign in Bangi village, Mariga LGA, the joint security task force in Niger state neutralized 100 suspected bandits (Omonobi, 2022). Similarly, in another operation within the same month and state, security agents reportedly killed over 200 bandits and recovered numerous stolen items, including motorcycles and livestock (Obiezu, 2022). In October 2021, the joint security forces comprising the police and the military neutralized 32 bandits attempting to flee from the forests of Zamfara into Niger State (Sahara Reporters, 2021). Further efforts were recorded in June 2022 when members of Operation Yaki and the Kaduna State police eliminated four bandits and arrested a woman suspected of supplying weapons to the group (Lere, 2022). Additionally, Operation Safe Haven, a collaborative security initiative in Southern

Kaduna, trained 975 personnel from the state's vigilante network in basic combat and firearm usage. This initiative was aimed at addressing manpower shortages and fostering greater coordination among security agencies (Alabelewe, 2022). Despite these military and policing successes, including the dismantling of hideouts, the capture or elimination of numerous bandits, and the recovery of stolen assets, banditry persists. The continued prevalence of these attacks indicates deeper systemic issues within Nigeria's security architecture. Specifically, persistent insecurity has been attributed to inadequate police resourcing, over-dependence on militarized security measures, and a consistent breakdown in actionable intelligence.

Concluding Remarks: Making a Multifaceted Governance the Epicenter of Counter-Banditry

Despite the implementation of various strategies aimed at addressing the menace of armed banditry in northwestern Nigeria, these measures have largely fallen short of delivering sustainable results. The continued reliance on military counter-banditry and counter-insurgency tactics has led many analysts to question the efficacy of Nigeria's security approach. Military-oriented security strategies, particularly in the North-West, have not only failed to suppress the insurgency but in some cases have inadvertently intensified the conflict. Community-based interventions, such as the use of local forces and vigilante groups, have sometimes exacerbated violence rather than curbing it, undermining broader security efforts. The persistence of these challenges underscores the need to reconsider the governance framework underpinning Nigeria's security management. Addressing the structural drivers of conflict, particularly governance deficits, is fundamental. Reorienting efforts away from a militarized security strategy toward inclusive, participatory governance that focuses on social welfare, justice, and equity could significantly reduce insecurity in the country. In this context, adopting governance models that ensure the effective management of both human and material resources is vital. By tackling deep-rooted socioeconomic inequalities, such as poverty, unemployment, and limited access to justice, Nigeria can begin to dismantle the conditions that fuel insecurity. Restoring public trust through community engagement and poverty alleviation programs tailored to the most vulnerable populations is also essential.

With a population exceeding 200 million, Nigeria's security forces remain grossly under-resourced. The ratio of 371,800 police officers to the population is far below the United Nations' recommended threshold of one officer per 450 citizens (1:450). Additionally, the deployment of officers is often skewed in favor of elite protection, serving politicians, wealthy individuals, and business figures while rural populations remain underserved and exposed to criminal violence. The police institution itself suffers from chronic underfunding, inadequate equipment, insufficient training, and low morale. A centralized policing structure further impairs responsiveness, creating a disconnect between security agencies and the communities they are meant to protect. Considering these limitations, decentralizing policing through community-based models that integrate local personnel familiar with regional geography and socio-political dynamics may prove more effective. These models allow for quicker threat detection and a more culturally sensitive approach to law enforcement, thereby improving the state's capacity to respond to local challenges.

The state's overwhelming dependence on militarized solutions has not caused lasting peace. A key reason is the insufficient appreciation of local contexts and conflict dynamics, which has led to strategic and operational missteps. While non-state actors, particularly vigilante groups, have been deployed, instances of extrajudicial killings and human rights abuses by these actors have only heightened tensions. In addition, arms trafficking has fueled the escalation of violence, highlighting the urgent need for more robust border control and arms monitoring systems. Nigeria's current border surveillance infrastructure is outdated and inadequate, especially in regions where state presence is minimal. Adopting advanced surveillance technologies to monitor porous borders,

particularly those shared with Niger, Chad, and Cameroon, could help mitigate the influx of small arms and light weapons (SALWs). Meanwhile, climate change and poor resource management have contributed significantly to the evolution of armed banditry. Deteriorating environmental conditions have forced pastoralists to migrate in search of arable land and water, often leading to clashes with indigenous farming communities over resource access. The Nigerian government has paid insufficient attention to these underlying environmental triggers. Furthermore, failure to involve local stakeholders in policymaking has further weakened the implementation of conflict resolution strategies. Additionally, corruption within the military and police leadership has undermined Nigeria's national security architecture. Funds meant for defense procurement have reportedly been diverted for political patronage, resulting in the poor equipping of security operatives and the weakening of operational capabilities. To address these systemic challenges, there is a pressing need to reform Nigeria's security leadership and introduce technologically savvy, well-trained professionals capable of managing modern security demands. Enhancing intelligence capacity and strategic oversight is crucial for reforming the country's security apparatus. Finally, traditional rulers and religious leaders who enjoy high levels of trust and influence within their communities can play a pivotal role in conflict mitigation. By engaging these leaders in intelligence gathering and peacebuilding efforts, the state can strengthen community-based security frameworks. Institutionalizing their roles through legal and constitutional recognition will ensure their formal involvement in maintaining local peace and supporting governance. Ultimately, transitioning to a people-centered security model that integrates local knowledge, promotes inclusivity, and builds sustainable peace structures is essential for resolving the persistent insecurity plaguing Nigeria's North-West and beyond.

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